

DECOMPOSITION OF ORGANIC HALOGEN COMPOUNDS BY ULTRASONIC WAVES. PART II. MECHANISM OF THE DECOMPOSITION OF METHYLENE DICHLORIDE IN AQUEOUS SOLUTIONS

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Aqueous solutions of CH_2Cl_2 , subjected to ultrasonic waves (1.2 Mc/s, 225 watts electrical input to the transducer) liberate chlorine (0.0149 g. atom per g. mole of CH_2Cl_2 in 3 hours) with the simultaneous formation of a yellow-coloured solid. With longer exposures, the liberation of chlorine does not seem to increase much. Pure undiluted CH_2Cl_2 fails to be decomposed by the waves. However, with dilution the liberation of chlorine increases and finally reaches a value of 1.473 g. atom per g. mole of CH_2Cl_2 at 0.1% approx. A considerable amount of bulk effect is observed. The decomposition is of zero order to a greater extent at both the frequencies tried and is favoured at the lower frequency. The reactions proposed are :

followed by hydrolysis and polymerisation.

Schmidt, Johnson and Olson (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 51, 370), while studying the oxidising action of ultrasonic waves, observed that aqueous carbon tetrachloride containing potassium iodide and starch became intensely blue; carbon tetrachloride and silver potassium bromide (two phase system) imparted a yellow coloration to water.

A similar observation was recorded by Liu and Wu (*ibid.*, 1934, 56, 1005) who remarked that the activated oxygen, produced under the influence of ultrasonic waves, liberated chlorine from carbon tetrachloride and chloroform in aqueous solutions. Kling and Kling (*Compt. rend.*, 1946, 223, 1131), while studying the influence of ultrasonic waves on halogen-substituted hydrocarbons, reported the liberation of halogens in detectable quantities which could be tested with silver nitrate solutions. The rupture of C—Cl bond was also observed by Surova (*Doklady, SSSR.*, 1953, 90, 1083) while studying the decomposition of the aqueous solutions of sucrose in presence of carbon tetrachloride under the influence of ultrasonic waves and they further stated that no cleavage of C—Cl bond took place in non-aqueous medium. The decomposition of aqueous solutions of carbon tetrachloride by ultrasonic waves was studied by Weisler *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 1769) and they proposed a mechanism also.

In a series of papers the present authors have attempted a study of the decomposition of organic halides under the influence of ultrasonic waves, e.g., carbon tetrachloride, methylene dichloride, ethylene dichloride and dibromide and chloroform. It has been observed that none of them except chloroform decomposes in pure state whereas all of them liberate halogens, when subjected to ultrasonic waves in aqueous solutions, in ionic as well as molecular form and simultaneously produce polymerised solids.

In the present paper, the sono-chemical decomposition of methylene dichloride has been studied which is comparatively a simple substance. It is a liquid, having B.p. 40° and a solubility of 2 g./100 c.c. in water.

Methylene dichloride also furnishes solid products in traces when subjected to ultrasonic waves. This product is very much similar to the one obtained in the case of

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ethylene dichloride. This may be due to the breaking of a C—Cl bond and thereafter to the presence of (CH_2Cl) radical in the former case and to $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}$ in the latter; these free radicals finally polymerise to solid products.

It is of interest to point out here that methylene dichloride in pure undiluted form did not decompose under the influence of ultrasonic waves. The pure sample was taken in an H-shaped tube; one arm containing the sample and the other, indicator for chlorine or chloride ions, and the waves were passed for half an hour. No traces of free halogen or halide ion could be detected qualitatively.

The experimental results on the decomposition of methylene dichloride by ultrasonic waves are recorded under the following heads :

- (1) The effect of concentration and bulk on the decomposition.
- (2) The kinetics of the decomposition at two frequencies.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The source of ultrasonic power, as in the previous communication (Prakash and Srivastava, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1957, 208, 127), was a high frequency ultrasonic generator (Mullard Type E-7562) with a 1.5 K watt oscillator, generating up to a maximum of 375 watts radio frequency when used with a 2-inch circular disc of barium titanate transducer. All the work was done at 225 watts electrical input to the transducer and frequencies of 990 Kc/s and 2100 Kc/s. These frequencies were the resonant frequencies of the transducers and were measured with a sufficiently accurate wave-meter. At these frequencies there were maximum fountain and fog of liquid vapours inside the reaction vessel. The output of the oscillator was fixed by using a stabilised line supply.

The transducer was introduced in a bath horizontally so that the waves could be produced vertically upwards. It was always immersed under water and the level of water above the crystal was kept constant. The temperature was maintained by circulating water at a constant temperature through the bath.

FIG. 1

The most suitable reaction vessel was found to be a flat-bottomed ground glass stoppered pyrex flask of 100 c.c. capacity for 2100 Kc/s transducer and (flat bottomed ground glass stoppered) Jena bottle of 250 c.c. capacity for 990 Kc/s transducer. In conductivity experiments, a specially designed reaction vessel, as shown in Fig. 1, was

used. This enabled observations to be made at any desired time without stopping the generator, by sucking up the solution in the conductivity cell for a short interval and then again sending it back to the reaction vessel.

The reaction flask was clamped between two brass plates, the lower one was provided with a circular hole of diameter of 2 inches. The distances between the plates could be varied at will, according to the size of the reaction vessel, with the help of a nut and thread device. The upper plate was fixed to a long range spherometer which could move up to 6 inches with a least count of 0.0001 inches. The spherometer was attached to a stand and could be moved up and down. The arrangement of clamp and stand is shown in Fig. 2.

FIG. 2

The results were reproducible up to 6%, as shown in a previous communication Srivastava, *Vijnaan Parishad Anusandhan Patrika* 1958, 1, 191).

Estimation of Liberated Chlorine as Silver Chloride in the Decomposition of Methylene Dichloride.—Saturated solutions of G. R. Merck quality methylene dichloride were prepared in water and portions of 20 c.c. of these solutions were exposed to ultrasonic waves at 35° for different periods. The reaction mixtures after exposure were kept for sometime to allow the finely divided particles to settle down and then these were filtered. The filtrates were estimated gravimetrically for chloride after the conversion

of free chlorine and hypochlorous acid formed, if any, into hydrochloric acid by reduction with sulphurous acid. The results are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Frequency = 2100 Kc/s. Power input = 225 watts. Temp. = 35°.

Vol. of soln. = 20 c.c. CH_2Cl_2 taken = 0.40 g.

Exposed for (in hr.)	$\frac{1}{2}$	1	1 $\frac{1}{2}$	2	2 $\frac{1}{2}$	3	3 $\frac{1}{2}$
AgCl formed (g.)	0.0028	0.0030	0.0036	0.0056	0.0080	0.0100	0.0102
Cl in CH_2Cl_2 (g. atom/g. mole)	0.0042	0.0045	0.0054	0.0085	0.0121	0.0149	0.0160

Effect of Concentration on the Decomposition of Methylene Dichloride.—Methylene dichloride solutions in 4 different concentrations were prepared by adding water to saturated solutions, and 20 c.c. portions of each of these solutions were exposed to ultrasonic waves for a period of 3 hours. The liberated chlorine was estimated gravimetrically as silver chloride, as described in the previous section. The results are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

[Conditions same as in Table I excepting CH_2Cl_2].

CH_2Cl_2 taken (g.)	0.4000	0.2000	0.1000	0.0200
AgCl formed (g.)	0.0100	0.0266	0.0486	0.0474
Cl in CH_2Cl_2 (g. atom/g. mole)	0.0149	0.0790	0.2887	1.4030

Effect of Bulk on the Decomposition of Methylene Dichloride.—Different volumes of saturated solutions of methylene dichloride were exposed to ultrasonic waves and changes in conductivity with time were noted. The results are shown in Fig. 3.

FIG. 3

Determination of the Kinetics of the Reaction.—A saturated solution of G.R. Merck quality of methylene dichloride was prepared in conductivity water (conductivity 2.2×10^{-6}). Then 15 c.c. and 5 c.c. portions of the saturated solutions were made up to 20 c.c. by adding conductivity water; 20 c.c. portions of the saturated solution and each of the subsequently prepared solutions were exposed to ultrasonic waves and the changes in conductivity were noted. The results are shown in Fig. 4.

The same experiment was repeated with a saturated solution of methylene dichloride at 990 Kc/s, as shown in Fig. 4.

FIG. 4

DISCUSSION

From the observations recorded in Table I, it is clear that with the saturated solution of methylene dichloride (about 3%) the amount of chlorine liberated per g. mole of the substance during the course of 3 hours of ultrasonic exposure (225 watts input and 2100 Kc/s) is about 0.05 g. atom, and with the increased exposure, it does not appear to be increased much.

The results recorded in Table II, however, show that if dilute solutions of methylene dichloride are taken, the amount of chlorine liberated is finally raised to 1.4 g. atom/g. mole of the substance at about 0.1% approximately. If the total halogen is released, as may be expected at higher dilutions, the value should be finally 2 g. atom of chlorine per g. mole of methylene dichloride.

Mechanism of the Decomposition.—It may be expected that the reaction proceeds in three different ways simultaneously. One of the fundamental sono-chemical reactions is believed to be the decomposition of water, as shown by the reaction (Prudhome

et al., *J. chim. phys.*, 1953, 50, 107; 1950, 47, 795; 1949, 46, 323; Weisler *et al.*, *Chem. Eng. Progress Symposium*, No. 1, p. 47; Hughes, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 225; 1935, 255; 1937, 1183; Frensdorff and Clark, *J. chim. phys.*, 1950, 47, 399; Hine, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 2438):

involving the breaking of H and OH with the consumption of 118 K cal. per g. mole. Simultaneously the sono-chemical decomposition of methylene dichloride may take place as shown below:

This necessitates the consumption of 68 K cal. for the breaking of C—Cl bond.

Following these two reactions, a number of side reactions may take place. Two types of mechanism may be suggested: one involving the hydrolysis and oxidation and the other, polymerisation and chain termination.

Hydrolysis and Oxidation Mechanism.—In order to explain the various steps it will be interesting to follow, at least so far as the hydrolysis is concerned, the chains postulated by Hughes and co-workers (*loc. cit.*) (SN_1 , SN_2 & E_2). Here it may be of interest to refer the three alternative mechanisms described by Hine (*loc. cit.*) for the basic hydrolysis of chloroform, suggesting CCl_2^+ as an intermediate.

Assuming the reaction (1) to be the primary sono-chemical reaction followed by the hydrolysis of methylene dichloride, promoted by ultrasonic waves, the following set of reactions may be suggested:

followed by:

The radicals Cl and H, formed in the sono-chemical reactions, may combine to give:

Polymerisation and Chain Termination.—Assuming the primary sono-chemical reaction to be one expressed by the reaction (2), the following reactions may be suggested to be taking place:

where X and Y may be Cl or H.

Kinetics of the Reaction.—The kinetics of the reaction at 2100 Kc/s is of zero order, which indicates that the reaction is proportional to the intensity of waves. This is analogous to perfect photochemical reactions in which the velocity is proportional to the intensity of light. The graph indicating the changes in electrical conductivity with time for three concentrations of methylene dichloride have been plotted in Fig. 4 and these are straight lines. It is clear from Fig. 4 that the reaction is favoured at a lower frequency.

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ERRATA

Page	Line	Read	For
60	Table IV, Column, 1 lines 2 & 3	in %).	in g.).
251	8	1908, 88, 745	1908, 88, 735
252	5	1957, 34, 35	1947, 34, 35
253	32	m.p. 213–15°	m.p. 213–25°
501	Table III, last line, Column 5	28.0	0.28
	„ 6	25.0	0.25
675	21	5.6 × 10 ⁸	5.6
709	23	the last two	the last three